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Introduction

- Inadequate seed quality and inconsistent sowing result in gaps within crop fields.
- Understanding these gaps is crucial for:
 - Enhancing sowing management practices
 - Assessing the impact of gaps on overall yield
- Gap detection during the germination stage facilitates timely reseeded.
- Objectives:
 - Gap detection
 - Gap length estimation
 - Filling point proposition

Methodology

Data:

- Corn field: 0.53 acres, 21 rows, 16720 plants
- Drone: DJI Inspire, RGB camera, GSD 0.9cm
- Min reseeding distance 45 cm -> 154 gaps

Plant detection, 3 methods compared:

- VARI index threshold
- Template matching
- Mask-RCNN

Gap detection steps:

- Line construction
- Line gap detection

Centroid-based connection of nearest detected plants

Formation of row lines through extended connections

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Results

Plant detection:

- Mask-RCNN is best at detecting corn plants

Model	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1 score
VARI	0.61	0.66	0.88	0.76
TM	0.52	0.55	0.91	0.69
Mask-RCNN	0.96	0.97	0.99	0.98

Ground Truth

VARI Thresholding

Template Matching

Mask-RCNN

Gap detection:

- Correctly detected 122/154 (79%) gaps
- Average gap length 56 cm, MSE 1.4 cm

Examples of results: true positive (1), true positive with incorrect length estimation (2), false negative (3) and false positive (4)

Conclusion

- Introduced a novel methodology for swift and precise sowing gap identification in corn fields.
- Significant advantages over traditional, manual methods and experience-based estimations.
- Plant detection, gap detection and length estimation are done with high accuracy.
- Data procured instrumental for optimizing resource utilization (e.g., water, fertilizers).
- Anticipate a yield enhancement of up to 5% with reseeded based on our findings.